

Metal Complexes of Fluorescein

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Fluorescein forms complexes of type $M \text{ Fl. } x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with Co(II) , Zn(II) , Cd(II) and Pb(II) , while metal ligand ratios are 2:5, 2:5 and 3:4 for Ce(III) , Th(IV) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ complexes respectively. The complexes isolated from an aqueous medium are insoluble in common organic solvents suggesting their polymeric nature. This is supported by their high decomposition temperatures.

IR studies reveal that all the three possible donor sites i.e. carbonyl, phenolate and carboxylate groups are utilised in coordination, the oxygen-metal linkages being of different strengths. From uv-vis spectral and magnetic studies of Co(II) complex a distorted squarepyramidal symmetry seems probable. An interesting observation made is that the temperature of the commencement of loss of water molecules is inversely related to the νOH values of the complexes, leading to the conclusion that stronger the H-bonding, lesser is the tendency of the loss of water molecules.

IN an earlier publication¹ the results of investigation on the Cu(II) complex of fluorescein obtained in an aqueous medium have been reported. Fluorescein forms solid complexes with a number of other metal ions also, and here the Co(II) , Zn(II) , Cd(II) , Pb(II) , Ce(III) , Th(IV) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ complexes and their characteristics are being described.

Experimental

Materials: Aqueous solutions of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH AnalaR), $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck), $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Albright & Wilson), $\text{Pb(NO}_3)_2$ (BDH AnalaR), $\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (BDH), $\text{Th(SO}_4)_2$ (BDH), $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Baker AR) and fluorescein disodium salt $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ (M & B Indicator) were prepared. Dil. mineral acid (1 or 2 drops) was added to the metal solutions to prevent hydrolysis.

Isolation of the Complexes: Since the free dye (acid form) precipitates in an acidic medium, the solution of the metal ion was kept in excess while precipitating the metal derivative of fluorescein. Hence, to 100 ml of 0.04 M metal solution, 50 ml of 0.04 M fluorescein was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complexes precipitated instantaneously, they were allowed to settle, filtered, washed with water and dried at room temperature.

Empirical formula: Microdetermination of C & H was done as usual. The amount of metal was known from the weight of residue left on ignition, wherever possible.

Spectral studies: IR spectra were recorded on a Grating Infrared-Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 577 using KBr pellets in the range $4000\text{-}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Uv-vis electronic reflectance spectra (ers) were obtained on a manual reading VSU-2P spectrophotometer using MgO as a reference.

Thermal studies: The tg results were obtained by heating at 10 min^{-1} .

Magnetic measurements: Magnetic measurements were done at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$) by Faraday method.

Results and Discussion

Composition and colour: Results on the composition and colour of the complexes are recorded below (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND COLOUR OF METAL FLUORESCEIN COMPLEXES

Empirical Formula	Colour	Carbon%	Hydrogen%
		Obs. (Calc.)	Obs. (Calc.)
$\text{CoC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark brown	52.80 (53.08)	4.15 (3.76)
$\text{ZnC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brick red	54.83 (54.42)	3.84 (3.40)
$\text{CdC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light brick red	47.73 (47.43)	3.81 (3.36)
$\text{PbC}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange	43.60 (43.24)	2.32 (2.18)
$\text{Na}_4\text{Ce}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5)_5 \cdot 13.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Red brown	53.15 (52.98)	3.96 (3.40)
$\text{Na}_2\text{Th}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5)_5 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange	51.31 (50.89)	3.10 (3.05)
$\text{Na}_2(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5)_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Red	40.22 (40.14)	2.98 (2.67)

*For correspondence.

Ignition residues : On ignition of the complexes in air corresponding metal oxides are expected as residues. In the cases of Co(II), Zn(II) and Pb(II) complexes, the amount of the residues correspond to oxides. Since, Ce(III), Th(IV) and UO₂(VI) complexes contain Na also, the residues consist of a mixture of oxides (Table 2). In general, the metal contents calculated from the residues correspond with the empirical formulae. Discrepancy in the case of cadmium complex is probably due to possible sublimation of CdO at higher temperatures⁽²⁾.

TABLE 2—IGNITION RESIDUES

Complex	Material on ignition	Amount taken (mg)	Residue Obs. (Calc.)	Metal % Obs. (Calc.)
Co(II)-FL	Co ₃ O ₄	4.040	0.740 (0.720)	13.45 (13.02)
Zn(II)-FL	ZnO	3.959	0.750 (0.731)	15.22 (14.83)
Cd(II)-FL	CdO	4.075	0.610 (1.035)	13.10 (22.22)
Pb(II)-FL	PbO	3.990	1.670 (1.603)	38.86 (37.30)
Ce(III)-FL	2CeO ₂ + 2Na ₂ O	3.945	0.800 (0.815)	12.14 (12.39)
Th(IV)-FL	2ThO ₂ + Na ₂ O	3.855	0.940 (0.965)	19.17 (19.63)
UO ₂ (VI)-FL	U ₃ O ₈ + Na ₂ O	3.739	1.440 (1.422)	30.42 (29.85)

Solubility : The complexes do not dissolve in common organic solvents viz. ethanol, chloroform, ether, carbon tetrachloride, *n*-hexane, benzene and nitrobenzene etc. They are sparingly soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. The insolubility suggests their polymeric nature^{5,4,5}.

Infrared spectra : The important IR bands of the ligand are compared with those of the complexes (wave numbers are expressed in cm⁻¹) Table 3.

A band at 1678 in the ligand, assigned to ν C=O, is not observed in the complexes in this region. This band generally shifts to lower frequencies on complexation^{6,7,8}, here it gets overlapped with ν_{asym} COO⁻ band and therefore is not prominently located. In some cases it appears as a shoulder on this band. The shift in ν C=O is taken as a measure of the strength of M-O bond^{7,8,9} and greater the shift in ν C=O, stronger is the M-O bond. Thus the complexes of different metal ions may be arranged in order of strength of M-O bond (related to C=O bond) as :

The ν C-O⁻ (phenolate) band observed in the ligand at 1310 shows a shift to higher frequencies in all the complexes, indicating its involvement in complexation¹⁰. Also greater the shift, stronger is the M-O bond¹¹. Thus the complexes may be arranged in order of strength of M-O (phenolate) bond as follows :

In all the complexes ν_{asym} COO⁻ (at 1593) decreases while a very slight increase is observed in ν_{asym} COO⁻ (at 1382). Hence COO⁻ to metal link is predominantly ionic in nature. The relative values of ν_{asym} COO⁻ give an indication of the proportion of ionic character of the link^{12,13}. Thus the order of increasing ionic character is -

Two strong bands in the ligand at 1260 and 1240 may be assigned to ν (C-O-C)¹⁴. They are not separately observed in the complexes and show positive shift on complexation, excluding the possibility of the coordination of this oxygen to metal in such cases^{15,16}.

TABLE 3—IMPORTANT IR BANDS OF FLUORESCEIN AND ITS COMPLEXES*

	ν OH(H ₂ O)	ν C=O	δ H ₂ O/ring	ν_{asym} COO ⁻	ν_{sym} COO ⁻	ν C-O ⁻	ν (C-O-C)
Na ₂ FL	3280-3200b,w	1690-75b	1635m	1592vs	1385s	1310s	1260, 1240s
Co(II)-FL	3480b, m	1552 s	1635sh	1578s	1388s	1312sh	1275s
Zn(II)-FL	3420b, m	—	1630m	1578s	1390s	1328s	1275sh
Cd(II)-FL	3570b, m	—	1630m	1570s	1388s	1322s	1281s
Pb(II)-FL	3440b, m	1545sh	1630m	1570s	1388s	1324s	1282s
Ce(III)-FL	3420b, m	1540sh	1633m	1577s	1390s	1325s	1303s
Th(IV)-FL	3420b, m	—	1630m	1570s	1385s	1320s	1295s
UO ₂ (VI)-FL	3460b, m	1533m	1630m	1575s	1390s	1325sh	1282s

*s-strong, m-medium, w-weak, sh-shoulder, b-broad.

Since the ligand is hygroscopic, bands due to $\nu_{OH}(H_2O)$ and δH_2O or/and ring vibrations¹⁷ appear at 3280-3200 and 1635. Occurrence of these bands in all the complexes indicates the presence of lattice and/or crystallisation and/or coordination water¹⁷. Very broad nature of OH bands probably suggests different types of H-bonding which may be a consequence of several oxygens in the ligand. However, no bands could be observed in the region 1100-700 assignable to wagging, twisting and rocking modes of H_2O , showing that the nature of metal to oxygen (of H_2O) link is not predominantly covalent.

A strong band at 918 observed only in $UO_2(VI)$ complex is the well known ν_3 band of $UO_2(VI)$ ion, a characteristic feature of all uranyl complexes¹⁴.

The structure of the fluorescein shows the three coordinating sites being so distantly situated that the possibility of any two sites being linked to same metal may completely be ruled out. Therefore, each site will most probably be linked to an independent metal atom and other coordination numbers of the metal will then be satisfied with different ligand molecules, thus producing a continuous three dimensional polymeric structure.

Electronic reflectance spectra: The ers of the ligand has a strong band (I) with its λ_{max} at 530 nm with three minor peaks on the lower wavelength side at 500 nm (Ia), 350 nm (Ib) and 270 nm (Ic), while the absorbance becomes zero at 235 nm. On the higher wavelength side absorbance decreases more rapidly but it does not vanish up to 900 nm.

In the ers of the complexes excepting Co(II), only intraligand bands are expected and any changes in the ers of these complexes may be ascribed to the ligand itself, while in the case of Co(II) complex bands due to metal ion in the ligand field are also expected. The ers of all the complexes show that in general band I moves to lower wavelengths (500-525 nm). While Ia could not be observed in any of the complexes, bands Ib and Ic generally move to lower values. However Pb(II) complex is peculiar in exhibiting a strong band at 560 nm.

Before discussing ers and symmetry around the metal ion it must be emphasized that although all donor atoms are oxygens, they are non-equivalent to each other and therefore, a perfect symmetry is completely ruled out¹⁸.

The ers of Co(II) when compared to that of other complexes, reveal three additional bands—first at ~390 nm, second at ~590 nm with a shoulder on its higher wavelength side and a third band of much weaker intensity of 875 nm. When these spectral bands of Co(II) are compared with the literature data^{19,20}, it is concluded that these neither compare with octahedral complexes, nor with tetrahedral complexes or with square planar complexes. However, according to Lions *et al.*,²¹ a weak band at 875 nm is characteristic of

square pyramidal complexes. In similarity to the reported spectrum for Co(II) squarepyramidal complex by Ciampolini *et al.*,²² the observed bands may be assigned as—

Bands	Assignment
390 nm (25.64 kK)	$^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4B_1$
590 nm (16.95 kK)	$\rightarrow ^4E$
875 nm (11.43 kK)	$\rightarrow ^4A_2$

Ciampolini and Nardi²³ in another communication found that suitable ligands for high spin five coordination should fulfill two main conditions: (a) donor atoms must possess strong coordinating ability and little tendency to form π -bonds and (b) the ligand must be bulky and polydentate one so that crowding around the metal ion should prevent a six coordinated configuration being attained. It may be seen that, fluorescein, satisfies both these conditions.

According to Gillespie²⁴, among the penta-coordinated transition metal ions, trigonal bipyramidal symmetry is favoured in largely covalent complexes, while essentially ionic bonding favours squarepyramidal symmetry and an intermediate structure is expected when bonding is intermediate in character. In the present complexes, as the ir study indicates, the bonding character (on the whole) is expected to be on the ionic side which further lends support to the distorted squarepyramidal symmetry.

Magnetic study: The effective magnetic moment for Co(II) complex has been determined to be 4.77 BM. But the value is at the lower limit of the range 4.7–5.2 BM observed for octahedral complexes and at the upper limit of the range 4.4–4.8 BM observed for tetrahedral complexes²⁵. For squareplanar complexes range is generally 4.8–5.2 BM. However, the observed moment is similar to some other Co(II) complexes having distorted squarepyramidal geometry²¹.

Thermogravimetric study: All the complexes contain water molecules, and generally in the primary stage of heating, these water molecules are expected to be lost. Excepting the case of cerium complex, in all others it is observed that in the initial stage slow

TABLE 4—THERMAL DATA OF FLUORESCIN COMPLEXES

Complex	$T_1(^{\circ})$	$T_d(^{\circ})$
Co(II)-FL	40	280
Zn(II)-FL	80	380
Cd(II)-FL	40	320
Pb(II)-FL	120	340
Ce(III)-FL	60	—
Th(IV)-FL	60	360
$UO_2(VI)$ -FL	60	340

weight loss occurs, which corresponds to water present in the respective complex. After this fast decomposition sets in. Table 4 records the starting temperature of initial stage weight loss (T_i) and decomposition temperature (T_d) for the complexes. In case of cerium complex this type of two distinct stages could not be observed.

From the Table 4, it may be seen that water loss starting at lower temperatures continues upto quite high temperatures. It appears that weight loss at lower temperature ranges is due to uncoordinated water molecules, whereas that at higher temperatures evidently signifies the loss of coordinated water. However, from the tg curves the two types could not be distinguished.

From Table 4, following is the order on the basis of T_i :

From the IR data (Table 3), the order on the basis of νOH in the different complexes is :

The above two orders are reverse to each other (Pb(II)-exception). Since lower νOH values indicate stronger H-bonding, it appears that the complexes having stronger H-bonding lose water molecules at higher temperatures.

Decomposition temperatures, T_d , for all the complexes are quite high (Table 4), which further support the polymeric nature. The decompositions of cerium, thorium and uranyl complexes are not complete even at 800° whereas for most of the reported complexes of these metal ions, the oxide level is reached at much lower temperatures².

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